

DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION OF CONVENIENCE FOODS USING JOWAR

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Abstract:

The present study was undertaken with an objective to develop ready to cook convenience products by using jowar. viz., ready to cook upama mix and Ready to cook Bisibele bath mix. Jowar grains were pre-treated and converted into semolina of different sizes (microns). Dehydrated vegetables were added to the ready to cook mixes. Further, upama mix and Bisibele bath mix were assessed for nutritional and sensory quality parameters. Further, these products were compared with control samples which are prepared by traditional methods. i.e, upama by wheat semolina and Bisibele bath by using rice. Results revealed that, nutrient contents specially minerals and crude fibre of jowar ready to cook mixes were higher compared to control sample. However, both the RTC products were well accepted in sensory quality assessment, hence these products can help to add value to jowar.

Key words: Jowar, Sensory quality, Convenience foods, Dehydrated vegetables

Introduction:

Sorghum is one of the major cereal crop consumed in India, after rice and wheat. It is commonly called as jowar or great millet. Sorghum is one of the coarse grain due to presence of outer fibrous bran of seed. Sorghum protein is superior to wheat protein in biological value and digestibility. It is poor in lysine but rich in leucine. The concentrations of thiamine, riboflavin and niacin in sorghum were comparable to those in maize. It is totally free from gluten, which bears impact in the present day scenario where the incidence of Celiac Disease (CD) an immunological response to gluten intolerance is on go up. Grain sorghum contains phenolic compounds like flavonoids which have been found to inhibit tumour development. (Vedaprakash D. and Madhavareddy, R.N., 2018). Sorghum lipids mostly consists of triglycerides which are rich in unsaturated fatty acids, oleic and linoleic acids. It also contains dietary fibre.

Convenience foods are type of food which imparts convenience to the consumer by way of little or no need of major processing or cooking before consumption. Rapid urbanization, phenomenon of working women, change in family composition due to working of couple at different places, consequent changes in eating habits of consumer have lead to development of instant mixes, ready to cook and ready to eat foods. Traditionally sorghum is used in preparation of roties which needs special skill and time to prepare roties. Convenience foods using sorghum may cater the needs of the jowar consumers both in terms of nutritional and psychological satisfaction. Use of sorghum in common foods such as Upama, Idli, dosa, sweets can be popularized for wider use in sorghum growing areas.

Instant mixes would be very useful at times for the easy preparation of the dish which is tasty, healthy and nutritious (Ranjani, V. and Sinthiya, R., 2018). Many processes are used in preparation of ready to eat cereals including flaking, puffing, shredding and granule formation in wheat, corn and rice but less research is available on

sorghum processing. Hence an attempt is made with an objective to prepare jowar processed products using semolina of different microns.

Materials and Methods:**Procurement of raw materials:**

Sorghum grains of variety GS-23 was procured from farmers field of village, Jagir nandihal, belongs to Raichur district of Karnataka. Dehydrated vegetables were procured from Department of Food Processing and Food Engineering, College of Agriculture Engineering, UAS Raichur.

Development of jowar value added products**Ready to Cook Upama mix:**

Upama is traditional and most common and easy to prepare breakfast dish of India. It is cooked as thick porridge using dry roasted wheat semolina. However, an effort is made to utilize jowar semolina in place of wheat. Further, different seasonings and vegetables are added during preparation.

Preparation of semolina from sorghum:

Semolina /rava from sorghum grain was prepared by taking cleaned sorghum grains. Then it was subjected to dehusking by treating the grains with 1 per cent water. Dehusking was done by hand pounding method. This can also be done using emerging machine. Later, husk was separated by winnowing. Further, grains were subjected to reduce the size (500 microns) by breakrules using semolina making machine. Semolina was separated from flour using sieve.

Methodology for preparation of Ready To Cook Upama mix

For preparing one kg of RTC Upama mix, 800 grams of dry roasted Semolina was required. To this semolina, 30 gms each of roasted urad dal and bengalgram dal, 10 gram each of roasted mustard, jeera and curry leaves were added. Dehydrated vegetables like carrot, beans, onion and green chilly were also mixed.

Jowar grits/semolina were dry roasted at separately for 5 mins

Bengalgram dal, urad dal, mustard seeds and jeera were dry roasted separately till the pleasant aroma comes

Dehydrated vegetables were added to the mix and packed in aluminium pouch

This upama mix was assessed for proximate composition according to (AOAC 1990)

Recipe for preparation of upama

Heat oil in a pan

Add RTC upama mix and sauté for 5 mins

Add boiling water (1:3 ratio) and cook till it gets soft

b. Ready to Cook Bisibele bath mix:

Bisibele bath, is a spicy rice-based meal with its origin in the state of Karnataka made of rice, lentils, spices and vegetables. In the present study, rice was replaced with jowar semolina and an effort was made

to develop ready to cook (RTC) *Bisibele bath* mix using jowar grits/semolina and other ingredients. For bisibele bath semolina was prepared without any pretreatment with higher micron size (600 microns)

Methodology for preparation of Ready To Cook bisibele bath mix

For preparing one kg of RTC bisibele bath mix, 600gms of sorghum semolina (600 microns) were used. To this 300 gms of redgram dal grits (by product obtained during milling of dal) along with 60gms of dehydrated carrots, 40gms of dehydrated beans were added. This mix also contain a spice sachet (Bengalgram dal, blackgram dal, Coriander seeds, fenugreek seeds, jeera, mustard seeds, pepper, clove, dry coconut, red chilli powder and salt) of 150 gms which needs to be added during cooking process.

Jowar grits/semolina and red gram grits were dry roasted at separately for 5 mins and 10mins respectively

All the spices were dry roasted individually till the pleasant aroma comes out blended in butterfly mixer grinder

Jowar grits and red gram dhal were mixed in the ratio of 2:1 and packed in aluminium pouch and spice mix sachet was inserted inside the pouch

Recipe for Bisibelebath preparation

RTC bisibelebath mix was added to boiling water (1:5 ratio) and pressure cooked for 12-15 min along with Salt and Seasoning with mustard and curry leaves were added to the cooked bisibelebath.

Proximate analysis:

RTC upama mix and RTC bisibelebath mix was assessed for proximate composition according to AOAC, 2000. Energy was computed by taking protein (4 kcal/g), carbohydrate (4kcal/g) and fat (9 kcal/g) values using the formula as per AOAC, (2000). The energy content of sample was calculated using the formula given below.

Energy (kcal) = [Protein (g) x 4] + [Carbohydrate (g) x 4] + [Fat (g) x 9]

Sensory evaluation:

The sensory evaluation of RTC mixes were carried out by semi trained judges using 9-point hedonic scale with score 9 as excellent and score 1 as disliking. Sensory evaluation was carried by 25 semi trained panel members. The sensory properties such as appearance, colour, consistency, flavour, taste and overall acceptability of finished product were evaluated on the basis of 9 point hedonic scale (Devaki and Premavalli, 2012).

Results and discussion:**Table-1. Nutrient composition of the jowar RTC bisibele bath mix**

Product	Moisture (%)	Carbohydrate (g)	Protein (g)	Crude Fat (g)	Crude fibre(g)	Total ash (g)
Control	8.81	80.84	9.15	1.25	3.56	0.79
Jowar bisibele bath mix	7.73	77.48	11.31	2.09	4.40	1.39

It is observed from the table that, moisture content of RTC jowar bisibele bath was less compared to control. This is due to the fact that RTC Jowar BB was dry roasted for easy cooking. It is also observed that protein (11.31 g) was higher in JBB (Jowar Bisibele Bath)

because of ingredients used in the preparation. With respect to crude fat and fibre, jowar BB contains more fat (2.09g) and fibre (1.39g) than control. This may be due to the fact that jowar contains more fibre and fat content compared to rice.

Table-2. Nutrient composition of the jowar RTC Upama mix

Product	Moisture (%)	Carbohydrate (g)	Protein (g)	Crude Fat (g)	Crude fibre(g)	Total ash (g)
Control	9.25	77.19	7.08	2.50	8.03	2.73
Jowar upama mix	9.02	78.31	7.04	2.82	8.35	2.81

Nutrient composition of RTC Jowar upama mix and control sample (Wheat semolina based mix) were depicted in the Table-2. Crude fibre (8.35g) and total ash (2.81g) content of Jowar Upama mix found to be more than control sample due to the fact that jowar contains

higher amount of fibre and minerals than wheat. Further, more carbohydrate content (78.31g) was observed in Jowar Upama mix than control (77.19g). However, protein content of Jowar upama mix was (7.04g) was on par with control sample (7.08g).

Table-3. Sensory evaluation of Jowar RTC products

Product	Appearance	Texture/ Consistency	Aroma/Smell	Taste/Flavour	Overall acceptability
RTC jowar bisibele bath	9	8	9	8	8
RTC jowar upama	9	8	8	9	8

Hundred gram of jowar bisibele bath mix and Upama mix was distributed to 10 subjects for sensory evaluation and results revealed that, the products found to be liked extremely by evaluators with respect to appearance whereas very much liked with respect to texture, overall acceptability. However, Aroma and taste of Bisi belebath and upama respectively were liked extremely.

Conclusion:

Overall, this Ready To Cook Jowar Upama mix and Ready To Cook Bisibele bath mix is highly convenient mix which saves lot of time,

tasty to consume and acceptable. Moreover, consumption of jowar can be enhanced which otherwise need a skilled person to prepare jowar bread/roti. Therefore production of RTC Jowar Upama mix and Bisibelebath mix can be a best alternative to jowar roti and good income generating source for farmers and SHGs.

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